

CLIMATE CHANGE - A NEW LOOK - PART TWO

DAMAGE TO THE EARTH'S ENVIRONMENT

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My paper "Climate Change - A New Look" was for many readers a little off beat. It included matters which I believe scientists have ignored; and many people have little conception of. This paper "Part Two" is about matters which governments and leaders of many countries have ignored to the detriment of the environment of the planet.

When I say "ignored" I really mean that governments have been too fascinated with new inventions that they have failed to foresee the need for regulation of matters which are now the main cause for concern about the future of life on this planet.

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INTRODUCTION

Most of the matters which will cause the threats to human life on this planet (now centred on global warming), have their origins emanating from the, so called, cleverness of people who have their ethnic origins in Europe. In the centuries before the two 20th century world wars, it was Europeans who were at the forefront of inventions which were supposed to make our lives more convenient; or to help us with obtaining the various commodities needed for living our lives. But during those earlier centuries, in Europe, the government of human affairs was divided between the controls coming from the kings or rulers and the regulations coming from the religious controllers. As the religious controls over secular matters waned, governments grew in power and gradually assumed control and regulation over all major matters which involved the living of a physical life. The regulation of the spiritual side of life remained with the religious types in most cases; yet there are many nations which are unwilling to keep religion and state government separated. Any regulation of the environment was seriously lacking.

This paper is about the failure of secular governments to foresee the future effects of the various, so called, "improvements" of our lives and to regulate them. Also for this paper I will include a fuller definition of the term "climate" so as to include such things as environment, surroundings, conditions and atmosphere, as well as the usual meaning of "weather".

When it comes to matters which affect the whole community and over a long period of time, we expect governments to regulate these matters with foresight. Such regulation must be done on a national level by governments. If they do not do it, then it may not get done. Some matters require international co-operation with respect to control and regulation. This, however, is rarely 100% successful over a long period of time.

THE INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTION

This revolution took place originally in Britain and spread to many European countries and later the USA; eventually affecting most of the world. It started in the 18th century (CE) and gained great momentum in the 19th century.

The main problem, which many people tend to either ignore or have little concept of, was the sense of being important, which is what happened to the government of Britain with the largest empire the world has recorded in history. When I say “ little concept of ” I mean to say that we as individuals are unable to realise that being the centre of attention leads to human mental blindness [see <https://www.academia.edu/45180280/>] This is a serious human failing; and in this case has caused the inability to perceive the effect of new inventions on our environment. Lack of foresight.

The effect of this blindness caused the British government to omit the full use of foresight or future planning. Hence when the lives of many people became improved in so many ways, the Government could not foresee that it would result in a population explosion. The UK population increased from about 10 million in 1800 to about 50 million in 1950. An average of more than ¼ million every year. This in turn meant that house building also exploded and cities like London started to get vast areas of houses with multiple chimneys puffing out smoke from coal heating fires.

COAL FIRE POLLUTION

The mining of coal increased rapidly during the 19th century as a direct result of the industrial revolution. Making cheap coal available for heating homes in place of wood.

Scenes like the one on the right were common. In the 1950's when I travelled to central London on the train I remember seeing these houses all puffing out smoke in the cold weather. It was in 1952 that the killer smog (smoke and fog) forced the UK government to pass the Clean Air Act which came into force in 1956. But its full effect took several years to benefit the air quality in London, due to slow reactions.

Several chimneys per house

This Clean Air Act was perhaps 3 or 4 generations after the explosion in house building. Here was the failure of government to foresee the effect of many thousands of houses, each with several fireplace chimneys, on the air quality of the city.

So we can see that the lack of foresight and future planning requires the problem caused to happen first, before governments act to try turn back the clock and correct their earlier omission to plan ahead. This gets very difficult with the passage of time.

What could the government have done? If they had realised that many thousands of houses, each with more than four fireplaces, would pollute the air of the towns, there are several things they could have done.

1. Limit the number of fireplaces to one per house.
2. Make it law that houses had town gas installed with gas fires.
3. Or have electric fires installed in living rooms instead of coal fires.
4. Have paraffin oil fires fitted into fireplaces instead of coal fires.

Town gas was available in London in the first decades of the 19th century. Electricity was available for houses before the end of the 19th century (1880s). Paraffin kerosene was available for heating before 1930.

Any one of these would have reduced the amount of pollution to the air of the cities. Yet it took several generations for the mistake of this omission to be realised and acted upon. This is what I mean by failure of government to foresee problems and regulate.

This blindness has not been cured by the smog experiences of the 1950's. It is amazing how soon human beings can forget. In 2020 alone 200,000 wood burning stoves were installed in the UK. There are currently millions of them in the UK and especially in cities like London where the old houses have fireplaces and flues which were previously used for coal fires. Currently approximately 17% of the particulate pollution in London's air has been attributed to wood burning stoves (GLA data). The current government has not restricted or regulated them. Will we get back to the pollution deaths of the 1950's ?

After the Great Fire of London in 1666 the UK government introduced many restrictions and regulations to prevent harm to the population from future fires. What happened to this awareness of harm coming from human actions? Was it because of the desire for taxation or simply the fascination of new inventions during the industrial revolution? Human mental blindness maybe!

MOTOR CAR POLLUTION

Governments of the UK became very excited by the mass production of motor vehicles, due to the revenue their sales would bring to the UK economy; hence they had another blind spot related to exhaust fumes. The same lack of foresight above, as applied to coal fires, applied to motor cars. It would be obvious to any person that the combustion engines in motor cars cause air pollution. The first cars puffed out filthy black smoke from the exhaust. This was clear to anyone. Thousands of cars puffing out toxic fumes was clearly a health hazard. Why did the government not regulate the number of cars in use throughout the country?

Allowing every one with enough money to own a motor car was a big mistake. The desire to have a car and having an essential need for one are not the same thing. Long before the 21st century lack of regulation has meant that many households have three car owners living at one address. Most old houses in towns do not have garage space. Apart from the parking problems this has given rise to, it has become one of

the worst causes of air pollution in London; and many cities across the UK and indeed the whole world.

When I was a child in the 1940s we played out in the street. It was rare to see a car passing along our road. About 3 or 4 people in the street had cars. People all used buses, trams or trains (or walk) to get to work and to the shops. Remember, we were approaching 50 million population in those days. Not having a car did not prevent life from going on. People adapt to the situation they find themselves in. But human desires are endless and generally uncontrolled. This is why regulation is necessary (e.g. alcohol, smoking, narcotics etc. are regulated)

In the following decades the vast number of people using a car to get to work has caused serious delays to public transport buses; even though many bus lanes have been introduced over time. Also the time to get work by car has more than doubled since the earlier years, meaning that many cars have engines running during this extended time, pushing polluting gases and particulates into the air.

Now the authorities are trying to regulate the number of cars on the roads through charges or taxation. In recent years a daily charge has been levied in London on all polluting cars. This is to reduce the sickness arising from excessive toxic fume pollution. This has caused the incentive to use a car, in preference to public transport, to become greatly reduced. Had previous governments regulated the ownership of cars many problems would not have occurred. And everyone would have lived their life OK.

But all this modern control through legal intervention has come, once again, several generations too late. If regulation of who would qualify as needing a motor car, was introduced in the earlier years of the mass production of cars, then many current problems related to excess cars could have been avoided. This would not have caused serious problems for citizens. If you had a real need for a car then regulation would allow it.

People adapt their lives to what they have. If they have car then they will use it for many unnecessary journeys; or take to working many miles from home needing two daily journeys. Without all this additional traffic and use of cars, public transport networks would have become more extensive and more well used. Making them more viable. Also the huge disruption and cost of constructing hundreds of miles of town by-passes and motorways could have been avoided. The more motorways which were built the more people took to using their cars instead of public transport. Needing bigger and bigger motorways. The UK government could not keep up with the continued increase in road traffic which they caused through lack of regulating car ownership. The M25 London orbital motorway is often referred to as the longest car park in the world (117 miles - 188 kilometres) due to slow moving traffic at busy times. Is it quicker travel? Maybe not.

In previous centuries in the UK goods were transported, almost pollution free, on an extensive network of canals. When I was a child most goods were transported by train. Every town had a goods yard at the local train station. The privatisation of the railways has made goods transport too expensive; hence the increase in huge lorries causing traffic and pollution problems. Governments have caused the rundown and removal of both canal and rail goods networks; by not realising the

trouble free and pollution free method they provided. The privatisation of railways was a big mistake by central government.

We are seeing multiple mistakes by governments, each of which seem to take several generations to realise. Then trying to turn the clock back becomes almost impossible.

There is much more to this motor transport pollution situation; such as tyre wear and brake lining particulates, not focussed as much as exhaust fumes. But, for example:- when it was clear that asbestos dust caused lung cancer, asbestos was eventually banned in vehicle brake shoes. A recognition that the air we breath is dangerously polluted with brake lining dust. But I must move on to the next example of government failure.

THE EXTENSIVE UNREGULATED USE OF ELECTRICITY

Electricity is a two edged sword. As well as being a convenient and valuable source of energy it has become one of the most harmful things in human history. The industrial revolution gave rise to the generation of electricity for use in factories and processing. The availability of electricity was soon extended to homes of the population. The house I lived in for a few years with my grandmother (1950s), had no electricity when I first lived there. We had gas lighting and a large battery to power the radio set. After a couple of years electricity was installed in all the houses in the road. Suddenly we had many new ways of living which were more convenient. This was a very late installation of electricity.

Across London this kind of development meant that every year thousands of new homes were demanding electricity from the national network. This in turn caused several large power stations to be built along the river Thames in London so as to supply the increased demand. In all, at least six coal fired power stations were built in the London area beginning in the late 19th century. All had tall chimneys which were supposed to convey the toxic fumes to the upper atmosphere. Yet in cold weather the fumes simply cooled and fell onto the surrounding city.

I worked in Southwark Street on the South Bank area of London in the 1960s. In the cold weather ash, and sometimes smoke, would come through the windows of our office from the Southwark power station; which was only a few hundred metres away. Such was the damage to the London air that all these power stations were decommissioned long before the end of the 20th century, replaced by power stations in areas remote from large towns and cities. Another huge mistake by the British government.

Southwark power station
Note:- falling smoke plume

As with the motor car, the British government has not considered regulating the use of electricity, especially for the domestic situation. Tens of millions of homes using a few unnecessary kilowatts of electrical energy at peak times, can cause the need for more and more power stations. This is what happened in the second half of the 20th century in the UK. And as with the motorway attempt to control excessive traffic away from towns and villages, the government could not keep up with the

increasing demand for electricity. Necessitating more and more power stations to be constructed, usually coal fired.

If a pricing regulation had been introduced, construction of many of these new power stations would most certainly have been avoided. How would that regulation work? Simply make a fair and acceptable assessment of electricity use for each dwelling based on size and number of occupants and real necessity. Then allocate these daily amounts to relevant dwellings. Then if the average over each week exceeded the allocation, the excess would be charged at ten times (or any agreed ratio) the normal charge. All houses have meters; hence it is not difficult to do this. This would force people to keep their electricity bills low by economising on their use of power. This is the civilised way to control this matter and to avoid the need for more and more power stations. Adjustable when more power is available.

When there has been low rainfall leading to water shortages causing restrictions, the same idea is used by applying penalties for people who use excess water (car washing and garden watering). Water is a far more vital requirement for human life, hence why cannot controls in the use of electricity be introduced?

When coal fire smoke showed that it was a mistake to use coal, the UK government passed the Clean Air Act which outlawed the use of coal as a fuel. Here the government did not delay in making a new regulation which would impact on people's lives. The pending future shortage of electricity is good enough reason to introduce a new law to ration its use. It shows that it was a mistake to allow unlimited use of electricity.

The new threat to carbon emissions is from the use of electricity to power smart phones and for their digital data storage. A surprising 11% (and growing yearly) of all power generated across the world is now used for telephone power and internet data storage. Much of this is due to the billions of smart phones used to make messages, pictures and videos and the streaming of sound and video files. Smart phone users do not realise that they are all contributing to climate change with their unnecessary use of the phone; also due to their data needing 24/7 storage.

Those who are not sure about this, it is as if they see the tiny grain of earth carried by an ant as doing very little. But look at the 2 m diameter and 1.5 m high ant hill and see what 100,000 ants have done. The Chinese proverb "large pot is filled with small drops" is relevant here. But who would think to regulate the use of smart phones? There are billions of smart phones. Now this single item is rivalling air travel for its contribution to CO₂ emissions into the environment. And to be honest, most of the use and the data people generate through their use of phones is entirely 100% unnecessary for a healthy life. Or could be done in other ways.

Many of these people would probably support the "climate change" protestors, but not realise that they could live quite happily, and more so, without a smart phone and thereby contribute to reducing climate change. No-one has thought that this tiny use of electricity needs to be regulated; as with most other uses of electricity. The small bits add up when there are billions of them. Human desires are endless and uncontrolled; and are causing damage to the environment in which we live. Here is another real need for regulation.

Such is the current increasing rate of data storage power use, that some authorities are concerned that there will become a power shortage in the near future. Data centres will not be switched off so perhaps domestic properties will have power cuts. Are power cuts a better way than regulation? Power cuts of several hours in Pakistan have caused riots.

THE USE OF NUCLEAR POWER STATIONS

The failure to do any kind of regulation of electricity use has resulted in the growing deployment of nuclear power stations. The same problem has occurred across the world; where there are more than 50 under construction and more than 90 proposed nuclear power stations (in 2024). We have all seen the effect of nuclear power station failure. (Chernobyl, Fukushima and Three Mile Island). The pollution of the environment with radio-active dust etc. This is a pollution which will not go away by any kind of government law or regulation. The same applies to nuclear waste from these power stations.

Some decades ago the political green parties were seriously opposed to the construction and use of nuclear power stations. Many marches and protests were organised across the world to request that governments did not ignore the risks of nuclear waste causing a health problem for current and future generations. But due to the scientists promoting their idea of "Climate Change" (see my paper "Climate Change - a New Look") the green parties have become ominously silent on nuclear power; because they falsely believe it poses less risk to the climate; and even prevents the use of fossil fuels, meaning less CO² emissions. They are also clearly suffering from human mental blindness (HMB).

Even now governments do not know what to do with the toxic waste from nuclear power stations, which can remain dangerous for hundreds (or thousands) of years. Why do they not simply regulate and limit the use of generated electricity and obviate the need for nuclear power? The full cost of construction of nuclear power stations and the many years of decommissioning costs and dealing with the waste storage over many decades, is not declared or counted by governments. If the truth were admitted, it is really much more expensive than other methods. There is no justification for its use.

Here we have another serious mistake by governments across the world. We say "kicking the can down the road". i.e. leaving the nuclear waste problem for a future generation. This is both immoral and seriously damaging to our environment. Nuclear waste is likely to become more of a long term risk to human survival on this planet than any effect of climate change. All because no-one saw the need to regulate or limit electricity use.

Several countries in the world have seen the light of the nuclear power subject and have phased out or stopped their use of nuclear power generation. If all countries were to begin the regulation of electricity use, it would remove the need for this dangerous human action. Now is the time to do it and dump the nuclear power option.

CRUDE OIL PLASTIC PRODUCTION

Here we have another subject which should have been more closely controlled by government. Most modern plastic comes from crude oil refinement. An earlier form of plastic type material was called cellulose derived from plant material. A later development produced celluloid, the plastic used in film making. Most of these plant based plastics would break down in a short time and become reabsorbed into the natural environment. This however was the incentive behind the production of crude oil based plastics. It was thought to be "clever" to produce a plastic which was not subject to environmental breakdown. Why did this not ring alarm bells in the minds of government controllers? A long lasting material, which would obviously produce waste products due to being discarded after use, would clearly present problems for the natural environment, due to it remaining without decomposition. More human mental blindness.

Governments should have insisted that producers of all plastics could produce them in such a way that they would eventually be broken down and reabsorbed into the natural environment. They could have done this. But governments did not foresee this situation. Now the natural environment is clogged with discarded long lasting plastic materials. It was possible to make plastics which would have a life related to their expected use and would become compost or food for either bacteria or other small creatures. Scientists could have done this; and it would have removed the problem from the planet.

This failure has caused the current situation of an estimated 171 trillion plastic objects to be amassed in huge floating islands in the earth's oceans. This plastic is killing birds, fish and mammals. Even with awareness of this there is an estimated 9 million tons of further plastic waste added to the oceans every year. It needs international co-operation and regulation to solve this. But there is none. All this plastic slowly breaks down into microscopic particles which are entering the food chain. (micro plastics)

In addition to plastic waste, "clever" people invented plastic fishing nets which do not break down in sea water. Now many thousands of these discarded nets are causing every kind of problem with boat propellers, wild life and divers etc. They are a dangerous hazard to so many people and animals. Was it really a clever thing to do?

Because of this failure of plastic controls the world is penetrated with micro-plastic particles which will not break down easily. These microscopic particles are in our blood and bones. This cannot be undone. No-one knows the long term damage this may do to organic life on the planet. Here is another failure of the controllers to foresee the danger of new inventions resulting from the industrial revolution.

THE INVENTION OF CFC GASES

Another "clever" invention by the scientists was the gas called Chloro-fluoro-carbon (CFC). There are about five different gases which were once used for such things as aerosol propellants, refrigeration, fire suppression and solvents. Like many of the above disastrous scientific (clever?) inventions the full effect of the new invention was not realised when it was first used; nor was it fully investigated. CFCs damage the ozone layer in the upper atmosphere; this atmospheric layer protects life

on the earth from the damaging effect of solar radiation. Mother Nature's way to protect the life She created.

CFC's were first used as a replacement to toxic gases used in refrigeration in the 1920s. It took 50 years for the damaging effect of CFCs on the earth's ozone layer to be realised. At that time there was a serious threat to all life on this planet. Then gradually the use of CFC's was outlawed in many countries. The Montreal Protocol (1987), which was internationally recognised, banned the production and use of CFC gases so as to protect organic life on the planet. Yet even now there are many countries who cannot afford to replace their old refrigeration systems and require CFC gases. These are illegally produced and smuggled around these countries. Such is the total ignorance of a section of the human race, that the annihilation of all life on the earth is less important than earning a few dollars producing and selling illegal substances. Much like the attitude of the narcotic drug producers and sellers. They have no concern about the damaging effects of their actions. This is human behaviour lower than any animal. And a threat to human life.

This situation with CFCs, as with all of these damaging inventions, would not have occurred if the industrial revolution had not happened in such an uncontrolled way. This revolution involved the many ideas of making our lives easier; when we had lived on this planet for an unknown number of millennia without such things. And life had continued without all these risks to survival. Have we really benefited if many live shorter lives?

We can say the same about the damage caused by unregulated use of the internet. How much cost and damage to people's lives has it caused. (clever??) We could have lived without it. At least a recognised ID (citizen number) should have been used for access to it.

OUTER SPACE JUNK

Another, so called, "clever" invention is the man made satellite; sent up beyond the upper atmosphere to perform a digital or computer function. But if we are honest this is not so clever. Why? You may ask. Because eventually the whole operation of getting them up there is going to affect the survival of organic life on earth. Forget the CFC problem; that one is to some extent resolvable. The potentially serious effect of this space junk problem cannot be reversed in our life time.

Currently (June 2024) there are nearly 6,000 satellites orbiting the earth; with 3,600 of these no longer performing any function. Within the next decade about 100,000 more satellites are planned; more than 16 times the current number. When thousands of these fail to function then many thousands more will be required to replace them.

Accidents and collisions in space are what cause the many small bits of space junk. These events are certain to increase when there are many more satellites. There are no traffic controls possible in space.

So far the operations involving satellites have produced an estimated 10,000 tons of debris suspended in space for an indeterminate period of time. This is after a proportion of it has burnt up on re-entry to the atmosphere, depositing toxic metal gases into the air we breath. The remaining space junk has resulted in an unknown

number of millions of objects ranging from 1mm to 100mm in size. Multiply this by 16 (100K /6K) and you can see that within a decade there will be so much rubbish up there that it will produce a 24/7 reflective shield reducing vital sunlight required for plants to grow and function.

Astronomers are definite that currently (2024) space junk is preventing a clear view of the stars in the sky. Does this not also mean that the sunlight is not fully reaching the earth's surface? This will get far worse in the next ten years. In past centuries we all lived without satellites. Believe it or not, we can now also! And with a better chance of surviving on the planet.

Where is the advantage of all these space computers up there if there are fewer human beings needing their service. Because without plants we have no food. And without food animal life cannot survive. Here is the potential threat to our existence.

Or will we produce 1,000s more power stations to provide artificial sunlight for food growing? The jury is still out on whether artificial light can really replace sunlight for healthy plant food production. We simply do not know how the wider spectrum available from sunlight affects the quality of the nutrients in food. This is another subject which could be a human technological mistake; taking several generations to discover. Also we can predict what will happen to the environment if we need many 1,000s more power stations. And remember if there is reduced sunlight due to space junk then the solar panels will be less effective.

Not one of the satellites put into space can continue to give service for ever. Hence in time when either, or all of, economies, human abilities or willingness of nations no longer put satellites into space, the services they provide will eventually cease. Human communities change and evolve over time, history has proved this. So the damage will be done simply to satisfy a passing fancy of the human race. Everyone falsely believes that digital things will be here to stay. Human history does not support this idea. The internet will self-destruct.

The "clever" technicians and scientists who have enabled satellite technology now join the inventors of CFC gases, motor cars and long life plastics, as destroyers of our planet and our healthy living on it. Now we must move on because there is more damage "in the pipeline" - as it were.

POLLUTION OF LAND AND WATER

The industrialisation of almost every nation on earth has created the conditions for the biggest population growth in the known history of the human race. Around the year 1,000 CE there are estimated to have been less than 100 million people on earth. This steadily increased to around 3 times that number by the year 1,500; a factor of 3 in 500 years. All these numbers are mere estimates as there are few records available. It was from the 19th and 20th centuries that the explosion from ½ billion to currently nearly 7 billion took place. A factor of 14 in 150 years. More than fifteen times the rate of population increase since the 16th century CE. This rapid increase was mostly due to the "clever" inventors and scientists of the industrial revolution, making life such that people could afford the time and cash to have more children.

With so many mouths to feed the farmers of all nations had to massively increase their production, especially as the increase in urbanisation of the populations meant that less people by proportion wanted to do farming. This huge

demand for more food meant that the inventors had to come up with ways to increase yield from the land. This generally involved chemistry. It was thought that to put chemicals onto the ground would increase the yield for farmers. Then there was the losses due to nature such as insects and other pests which reduced the yield of the various crops; fertilisers and pesticides.

It has long been known that rain water has two main ways to disappear from the land surface. Runoff into rivers and penetration deeper into ground water. Yet neither of these routes for rainwater were considered when toxic chemicals were put onto the land. Surely governments and scientists would realise that allowing toxic or damaging chemistry onto the land surface would not only pollute the land, but it would also pollute the rivers, through runoff and the drinking water through downward passage. Also wildlife would suffer from the toxins. How “clever” of the scientists to do this!

Not only farming but the requirement for more metals and coal increased the mining of these things, causing more pollution from the mines into ground water and rivers.

The poor management of sewage waste from the increase in population has also meant that land and water have become poisoned.

Approximately 3,500 BC the Harappan civilization in the Indus valley area, had large communities. They had bathrooms and toilets in every home. There is evidence that they channelled (or piped) the human waste onto the farms to make fertiliser. There is no evidence that they polluted the land. Why was this technology forgotten? Or was it?

When I was a student of civil engineering, in the 1960s, I remember a trip to an East London modern sewage works. Water management was the duty of local authorities in those days. I was impressed by the technology of separating the various types of effluent, and the solids from the water content. The water was treated with aeration using bacteria such that the toxic water became drinkable. The solids were dealt with again using bacteria in huge digestion tanks. This produced harmless sludge which could form farm fertilizer and gas which powered the whole sewage works through gas generators. There was no toxic waste remaining. This seemed to me to be the civilised way of treating waste from the various human activities. Seems like the revival of the Harappan times of yonder years (5,500 year time gap). The plan then, in the 1960s, was to install this technology across the UK.

When I left college my first civil engineering engagement was to work for a company in London which specialised in the design and construction of exactly the type of advanced sewage works which I had seen in East London. However, most of the projects were in countries outside the UK; which surprised me. These sewage works were complex and very costly. The size of a very large factory with many buildings.

Not long after this (1980s) one UK government decided to privatise the water companies across the UK. The result was water treatment for profit and shareholders cash. After that fewer water companies could afford to install the modern type of sewage works described above. This has resulted in a huge problem of sewage waste polluting our land, rivers and coastline in the UK. There are more

than 1,400 areas in the UK which require the treatment of sewage and waste water. Less than 40% of these have advanced sewage treatment works. All this, 60 years after I was so impressed with the situation then.

We have the technology to deal with this problem; but apparently, one of the richest nations in the world, does not have the cash available; So much for the benefits to the community of privatisation. Yet we can waste so much tax payers money on the useless efforts to colonise space, or send people to the moon. I can include here the very, very expensive idea that nuclear power is the way forward. Government regulation has not worked as well as a modern sewage works would have done.

All the above pollution and contamination problems can be laid at the door of government. The failure to act by successive incompetent governments across the world, has created this serious risk to human survival on the planet earth.

CONCLUSION

No-one has a human right to own a motor car. Neither do they have a human right to have the convenience of electricity or a smart phone. This is simply because human life can continue without these things. Although many people would not agree with me due to life styles being modelled around the convenience of such things being falsely thought of as normal life and essential. Prior to the industrial revolution all human communities lived here able to acquire all the food, clothing and shelter they needed. The human race has been shown by recent archaeology to have been here for at least 3 million years. This came from the discovery of woodworking tools recently found in Turkana in Kenya (Africa). Dated as being around 3.3 million years old. Nomads have little or no need for wood-working tools. Hence this shows, contrary to many "clever" scientist's previous pronouncements, that organised human societies have been on this planet for a longer time than they originally imagined.

With all the damage done to the environment of the planet in the last 200 years, it has now become unlikely that human civilisation will survive in its current form for another 100 years. A tiny proportion of the time we have been here.

Here is the stark reality of what governments have done by their failure to wake up from their mental slumber and regulate harmful inventions. And I am sorry to say that so much of this should be laid at the door of the British government due to the, so called, "clever" inventions of the industrial revolution.

When will the world wake up to the need for intelligent regulation? And for populations to make sure by one method or another, that their country is governed by a knowledgeable, intelligent and capable group of people, who will use foresight when big changes come.